

Impact of Bhagavad Gita Chanting on Emotional Intelligence of Secondary School Students: A Review

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between the Bhagavad Gita's teachings and emotional intelligence, with a particular focus on the significant benefits of the Bhagavad Gita chanting and its relevance to modern psychology. It explores how applying the Bhagavad Gita's teaching to daily life boosts emotional intelligence, resilience, self-awareness, empathy, and managing stress by examining various types of research and books of literature. The Bhagavad Gita's teachings and emotional intelligence are examined in this study, with a focus on how modern culture's stress management, self-awareness, endurance, and empathy may be enhanced by Gita chanting and other related practices. The research emphasizes the relationship between emotional stability and the teachings of the Gita. It also examines the effects of yoga, meditation, and chanting on well-being, particularly for teenagers, and how these activities support both emotional intelligence and academic achievement.

Key words: Emotional Intelligence, Intelligence Quotient, Emotional Maturity, Intelligence, Sthithaprajana, Bhagavad Gita, Mindfulness, Self-Awareness.

1. Introduction

The concepts of 'Mind' and 'Intellect' were defined in different Indian texts throughout history: Rigveda in the first era, Yoga Vasishta in the second era, Bhagavad Gita in the third era, and Vivek Chudamani in Kaliyuga. All the literature demonstrates that flexibility and firmness in behavior are key to success in all periods, akin to self-awareness and self-management in emotional intelligence (Goparaj & Sharma, 2011). Contemporary society has brought in a range of technological gadgets for young people, offering clear advantages, but also leading to emotional instability and dependence caused by addiction (Subbarayan & Visvanathan, 2011). Adolescence is a time of significant transformation characterized by quick physical, emotional, and cognitive changes. High School students frequently face increased emotional difficulties such as stress, anxiety, and peer pressure, which can hurt both their academic success and general state of health (Steinberg, 2014). Improving emotional intelligence (EI) at this crucial time can greatly improve students' skills in handling emotions, forming healthy relationships, and making well-thought-out choices (Goleman, 2006). The article seeks to evaluate the possible benefits of Bhagavad Gita chanting to emotional intelligence.

2. Bhagavad Gita

Described as the "Song of the Lord" the Bhagavad Gita is a popular Hindu text that is divided into 18 chapters and seven hundred verses. Given to Arjuna on the Kurukshetra battlefield by lord Krishna, tackles Arjuna's moral problem of participating in the conflict. The Gita can be useful not just in spirituality but also in psychology, particularly in the management of anxiety, depression, and negative emotions, as it provides instruction on maintaining mental balance and overcoming crises. It offers

Karma Yoga (unconditional action), Bhakti Yoga (faith), and Jnana Yoga (awareness) as the three main routes to spiritual realization (Tewari, 2022).

Hindus consider the Bhagavad Gita as a worshiped book. The Bhagavad Gita talks about divine insight, the self, and the accuracy of the natural cosmos. Reciting the verses of the Bhagavad Gita can result in multiple psychological and spiritual advantages, such as enhanced mental clarity, emotional steadiness, and inner tranquility (Feuerstein, 2008).

A Karma Yogi, known for their high emotional intelligence, achieves a state of steady equanimity (Sthitaprajna). This person represents intelligence, wisdom, transparency, forgiveness, honesty, and self-control, and remains unaffected by external situations. They attain self-realization and freedom from the cycle of birth and death by being free from delusion. This State of inner balance leads to mastery over both material and spiritual life (Goparaj & Sharma, 2011).

This paper attempts to relate the Bhagavad Gita to the emotional intelligence theory, particularly the capacity model of Mayer and Salovey. According to the Bhagavad Gita, a person who is emotionally stable and intelligent is a Sthitaprajna, when Arjuna Asked Lord Krishna who a Sthitaprajna is in detail (Gayathri & Meenakshi, 2013).

*Sthitaprajnasya ka bhasa samadhisthasya kesava,
Sthitadhih kim prabhaseta kimasita vrajeta kim. (In Sanskrit)*

Arjuna asked Lord Shri Krishna, O Keshav! What are the characteristics of a man of stable intellect who has attained the Supreme Being in Samadhi, how does he speak, how does he sit, and how does he walk? (Swarupananda, 1996). (Bhagavad Gita, Ch. II, Sloka 54).

*Prajahati yada kamansarvpartha manogatan,
Atmanyevatmana tustah sthitaprajnastadocyate. (In Sanskrit)*

Lord Shri Krishna said – O Arjuna when a man abandons all desires present in his mind and remains satisfied with the soul, then he is called Sthitaprajna. (Swarupananda, 1996). (Bhagavad Gita, Ch. II, Sloka 55).

*Duhkhesvanudvignamanah sukhese vigatasprah,
Vitaragabhayakrodhah sthithadhirmunirucyate. (In Sanskrit)*

The person whose mind does not get agitated on entering sorrows, whose mind does not get attached to entering happiness, and whose attachment, fear, and wrathfulness have been destroyed. Such a savant is said to have a stable intellect. (Swarupananda, 1996). (Bhagavad Gita, Ch. II, Sloka 56).

*Yah sarvatranabhisnehastattatprapya subhasubham,
Nabhinandati na dvesti tasya prajna pratisthita. (In Sanskrit)*

A man whose mind is steady, has no desire for anywhere and who is neither happy nor against anything good or uncomfortable. (Swarupananda, 1996). (Bhagavad Gita, Ch. II, Sloka 57).

*Yada samharate cayam kurmoanganiva sarvasah;
Indriyanindriyarthebhyastasya prajna pratiathita. (In Sanskrit)*

A man's intellect becomes stable after he completely disconnects his senses from sense objects, similar to what a tortoise does when it is attacked from the outside. (Swarupananda, 1996). (Bhagavad Gita, Ch. II, Sloka 58).

The Bhagavad Gita provides timeless guidance on do's and don'ts, resulting in an important tool for students can become successful and productive people by reading it from a contemporary, scientific standpoint, which will impact both their professional and personal lives (Kelkar & Mahajan, 2021).

3. Emotional Intelligence

20% of our IQ and 80% of our Emotional Intelligence are responsible for achieving something we achieve (Singh, 2021). The ability to recognize, understand, and control one's own emotions as well as the emotions of others is known as emotional intelligence (Salovey & Mayer, 1990). The collection of skills or characteristics associated with an individual's emotional life is known as emotional intelligence (Singh, 2004).

A combination of non-cognitive abilities, competencies, and skills affecting someone's ability to successfully manage demands and pressures from the environment can be referred to as emotional intelligence. Five main components of the Bar-On model:

1. Intrapersonal Emotional Quotient
2. Interpersonal Emotional Quotient
3. Adaptability Emotional Quotient
4. Stress Management Emotional Quotient
5. General Mood Emotional Quotient (Bar-On, 2000).

Mangal defined emotional intelligence in the Indian context as including:-

1. Intra-personal awareness (knowing about own emotions)
2. Inter-personal awareness (knowing about others emotions)
3. Intra-personal management (managing the personal emotions)
4. Inter-personal management (managing the emotions of another) (Mangal, 2004).

The article discusses the evolution of the theory of emotional intelligence (EI), how it differs from similar concepts, and the several EI models. It highlights how attitudes about emotions have changed from being disruptive to being important while making decisions. Emotions are distinct from physical sensations (emotions) in that they are a combination of ideas, feelings, and bodily experiences. Scholars like Mayer, Salovey, and Goleman have contributed to the evolution of the theory of emotional intelligence. Goleman stresses emotional skills like perception and regulation, whereas Mayer and Salovey's ability model concentrates on social skills like self-awareness and relationship management. Bar-On's trait model, which is hampered by self-report bias, connects emotional intelligence to well-being and stress management. The paper discusses problems with defining emotional intelligence and creating trustworthy evaluation instruments and offers criticisms (Gayathri & Meenakshi, 2013).

Empathy, operation, control over my emotions, self-awareness, and social skills are the basics of emotional intelligence. Greater levels of emotional intelligence are related to social interaction, mental health, and higher performance in school (Parker et al., 2004).

Students' social and emotional learning is neglected in many colleges and universities because emotional intelligence development is not given sufficient importance, despite its significance. Enhancing cognitive abilities, motivation, teacher-student interaction, Social-family connections, and improving overall confidence through social-emotional learning intervention (Zins et al., 2004)

4. Review of literature

Spiritual practices, that promote mental and emotional well-being include chanting, meditation, and prayer. Studies have demonstrated that these techniques foster resilient and positive emotional states by reducing anxiety, stress, and sadness (Koenig, 2012).

The study aimed to examine how yoga practices affected kids' general well-being and IQ. Thirty-five students, ages eleven to fifteen, participated in a 40-day yoga practice package that was randomly selected and given at the Yoga Arogya Polyclinic in Haridwar. The finding indicated a substantial increase in both IQ and overall well-being, indicating that yoga can improve these qualities in kids (Kumar, 2013).

Particularly, chanting has been linked to physiological and psychological benefits including a happier attitude and better emotional control, as well as physiological advantages like decreasing cardiovascular (Bernardi et al., 2001).

To increase well-being, this study investigates how implementing the Bhagavad Gita's teachings into practice improves emotional intelligence through enhanced self-awareness, resilience, empathy, and stronger interpersonal relationships (Bhakat & Das Biswas, 2024).

By providing advice on how to deal with stress, anxiety, and emotional difficulties, the Bhagavad Gita improves emotional intelligence. The study highlights karma yoga as a way to transcend emotions and integrate life skills for spiritual and economic success, and it shows a beneficial connection between Gita's teaching and emotional stability (Kondhalkar & Isave, 2022).

This paper presents feedback from students who participated in a Bhagavad Gita course at BITS Hyderabad from 2012 to 2019. Out of over 2000 students, 300 provided written input, and 28 alumni submitted their experiences. The course influenced three domains: increasing faith, improving mental clarity & concentration, and improving enduring qualities such as leadership and problem-solving abilities. Students proposed combining classic and innovative methods of teaching for better participation and intelligence (Lolla, 2020)

This paper interprets intelligence through the Bhagavad Gita, emphasizing the importance of emotional intelligence. It contrasts Western intelligence theories with ancient wisdom and explores Daniel Goleman's five emotional intelligence parameters from Gita's perspective. The paper argues that focusing on emotional intelligence, rather than just IQ, can offer sustainable solutions to modern challenges and lead to more purposeful lives (Lamba et al., 2023).

This study aimed to find out how the Bhagavad Gita affected college-bound students' emotional intelligence, maturity, and ideals. Two groups of Students Were formed for this. Wherein one group did not read the Bhagavad Gita while the other side used to read it. All of these learners were undergraduate, including in age from 19 to 21. The sample was created using a purposeful random sampling technique. Students reading the Bhagavad Gita exhibited higher levels of emotional maturity and moral principles than their non-reading counterparts (Raina & Balodi, 2014).

The study examined the impact of the CRAFT program (Focused on Mindfulness and Emotional intelligence) on 25 student musicians from the Royal Conservatory of Music Victoria Eugenia. Pianists and violinists were significantly present, with most attendees in their second or third academic year. The pre-post quasi-experimental methodology of the study was to evaluate the program's effects on participants' health and well-being. The CRAFT syllabus integrated concepts of emotional intelligence, mindfulness, and yoga into a whole day of instruction. The key concepts were awareness, calmness, concentration, satisfaction, and transcendence. Significant enhancements in psychological well-being, emotional control, and mindfulness were found by statistical analysis; certain effects that did not reach statistical significance were ascribed to lower dosage and individual variation (Bartos et al., 2022).

The study uses the exchange between Krishna, the lord, and Arjuna in the holy book of Bhagavad Gita to investigate how sympathetic listening affects the growth of emotional intelligence in engineers. The study surveyed 208 Indian engineers applying pre-established measures and paper-based questions. The result indicated that processing and responding to emotions were highly correlated with emotional intelligence, whereas sensing emotions was not significantly correlated with emotional intelligence. Based on the study, engineers who listen with empathy have greater emotional intelligence, although this process may be hampered by their focus on logical thinking. The study emphasizes how important it is to apply traditional wisdom to the development of emotional intelligence today and makes the case that listening with empathy is essential to emotional development (Mehta, 2016).

This study examined the relationship between disengagement (Anasakti) and resilience in the Bhagavad Gita and investigated gender differences in these variables among older people in south India. Analysis involving ninety-three people (forty-three men and fifty women) aged 60-85 years was examined. Results found a moderately positive connection between a lack of attachment and resilience. The study found not a significant gender disparity in the level of attachment; however, males demonstrated higher resilience than women. The study gives insights into emotional handling in older persons, revealing that while non-attachment is similarly dispersed across genders, resilience increases in older men (Rajeev & Hebbani, 2020).

This study examined the differences in life satisfaction, Anasakti (detachment), and resilience between readers of the Bhagavad Gita and non-readers. Using an independent t-test, fifty Bhagavad Gita readers and fifty non-readers between the ages of eighteen and thirty-five were analyzed. While there was no discernible difference in resilience between the two groups, it was found that people who read the Bhagavad Gita had greater levels of detachment and life satisfaction (Sharma, 2023).

The present research investigated how yoga changed the emotions, self-esteem, and control over emotions of adolescents from upper secondary schools in the Mandi area of Himachal Pradesh, ages

thirteen to eighteen. Of the 110 total pupils in the sample, 52 practiced yoga and the remaining 58 did not. Instruments that were specified were used to gather data. The results showed that compared to people who did not practice yoga, those who did had significantly better emotional control, self-worth, and regulation of their emotions. The results of the study highlight the need for yoga programs in schools by demonstrating how including yoga in the curriculum can improve the emotional and psychological health of adolescents (Janjhua et al., 2020).

An international firm in Bangalore, India studied the effects of yoga-based cyclic meditation on perceived stress and emotional intelligence (EI) of IT professionals using a quantitative study. The results showed that regular meditation practice raises emotional competence (EC), lowers perceived stress, and increases emotional quotient (EQ) (Srinivas et al., 2015).

The Study examined the relationship between academic achievement and emotional intelligence in a sample of one thousand upper-secondary students from a government school in Jaipur, Rajasthan. Using the application of a survey, it was shown that emotional intelligence has a favorable impact on academic achievement, specifically for girls (Mishra, 2012).

5. Conclusion

This study investigates the various manners in which the teaching of the Bhagavad Gita improves general well-being and emotional intelligence (E.I.). People may improve essential emotional intelligence skills like self-awareness, emotional resilience, empathy, and management of stress through practices like Bhagavad Gita chanting. The study emphasizes how beneficial these routines are, especially to adolescents, for emotional stability and achievement in school. Although the literature now in publication indicates a positive relationship between the teaching of the Bhagavad Gita and emotional intelligence. Further research is required to expand the scope of this relationship and improve the empirical data.

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